

Scaling Myself: Lessons from Engineering in Small, Mid, and Large Tech Companies

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Abstract—Organizational scale fundamentally shapes the way software is conceived, built, and delivered. Across more than a decade in the industry, I have worked in three distinct environments: a small company, a mid-sized company, and a large-scale technology enterprise. Each offered unique technical architectures, development processes, and cultural dynamics. This article contrasts these environments through the lenses of engineering practice, system architecture, and career development, offering actionable lessons for engineers transitioning between them.

Index Terms—Software engineering, organizational scale, distributed systems, cloud computing, system design, career development

1 INTRODUCTION

In software engineering, team size is more than a number; it is a determinant of how problems are framed, solutions are architected, and projects are executed. My career path, ranging from a 10-person small company, to a 300-person product-focused mid-sized company, to a global-scale engineering organization, provides a vantage point for analyzing the impact of scale on engineering practice.

This discussion focuses on three dimensions: development practices, system architecture, and career growth, with examples drawn from real-world projects, including distributed system design, AI integration, and large-scale cloud service optimization.

2 DEVELOPMENT PRACTICES ACROSS SCALES

2.1 Small Company (1–50 engineers)

Pace and Iteration: Rapid, with minimal process overhead.

Customer Feedback: Direct and often within days or hours – you actually get to meet the customers, which is exciting and gives immediate insight into how your work impacts them.

Processes: Lightweight CI/CD; informal QA; documentation optional.

Decision-Making: You have a lot of flexibility and can directly enforce decisions that shape the product’s direction.

2.2 Mid-sized Company (300 engineers)

Pace and Iteration: Structured sprints, agile ceremonies.

Customer Feedback: Mediated through product teams, but still responsive.

Processes: Formal code reviews, automated testing pipelines, coverage metrics.

2.3 Large Enterprise (5,000+ engineers)

Pace and Iteration: Governed by compliance and multi-team coordination.

Customer Feedback: Aggregated via telemetry, surveys, and product support data.

Processes: Multi-stage deployment approvals; extensive automated testing; full observability baked in.

3 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE IMPLICATIONS

3.1 Small Company

Monoliths common for speed; evolving architecture as product-market fit emerges. Tech stack chosen for developer familiarity, not necessarily long-term scalability.

3.2 Mid-sized Company

Service decomposition begins; microservices used to parallelize development. Standardized frameworks to manage growing complexity.

3.3 Large Enterprise

Distributed, fault-tolerant architectures spanning multiple regions. Example: Azure Copilot AI integration, designed with global availability, redundancy, and end-to-end observability, reduced detection time for incidents by 40 percent. Architecture review boards and formal change management processes.

4 CAREER GROWTH AND ROLE EVOLUTION

4.1 Small Company

Broad scope including design, development, and operations in a single role. Rapid skill growth, but limited mentoring structures. You can really reach a very high level in less time compared to larger organizations, since responsibilities and visibility come quickly.

4.2 Mid-sized Company

Specialization emerges; tech leads and domain ownership. Structured mentorship; leadership opportunities on small teams.

4.3 Large Enterprise

Highly specialized roles; ownership of critical subsystems. Leadership opportunities expand into cross-organization initiatives, architecture boards, and mentoring programs. Performance reviews are highly structured, often involving multiple levels of calibration. Competition for promotions can be intense, given the size of the talent pool and the formal advancement processes.

5 LESSONS LEARNED

- 1) Adapt to process scale. What works in a 10-person team may stall in a 10,000-person organization.
- 2) Balance speed with stability. Smaller organizations thrive on velocity, larger ones on predictability.
- 3) Preserve agility. Even in large organizations, pockets of innovation can move quickly.
- 4) Invest in breadth and depth. T-shaped skills enable success across all scales.
- 5) Expect cultural shifts. Technical adjustments are often easier than cultural adaptation.

6 KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM 10+ YEARS IN THE INDUSTRY

- 1) Being nice is not enough.
- 2) Respect comes from your work.
- 3) Innovation, participation, and mentoring are highly regarded.
- 4) Promotions and advancement need to be fought for anywhere.
- 5) Imposter syndrome is common and fades as you work harder and learn the system.
- 6) Work-life balance is in your hands.
- 7) You need to manage your manager.
- 8) There are no friends at work.
- 9) Modesty will make you obsolete; be visible, brave, and bold.
- 10) Communication triumphs over everything.
- 11) There is no fixed timeline to get promoted; you can climb or skip levels in as little as six months, regardless of team or organizational policy.
- 12) Networking will take you places. LinkedIn should be part of your daily routine. Prefer LinkedIn Learning and MasterClass for continuous growth.
- 13) Code, code, code. Do personal projects, shine on GitHub, and win hackathons.
- 14) Work on yourself, not just for the company.
- 15) You can be fired any day for any reason; be prepared financially and mentally.

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY

Ayush Goyal is a software engineering professional with over 10 years of experience designing and operating distributed systems across Azure and AWS. He has led high-impact initiatives, integrated AI-driven solutions at scale, and holds a patent-pending innovation in generative AI for marketplace listings. Ayush holds dual master's degrees in Computer Science and Analytics, and is passionate about mentoring, innovation, and building high-performance engineering cultures.

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